

Horizon 2020

Research and Innovation Framework Program

CHESS
SET UP

Deliverable D7.2 Graphical Identity of the project

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1. Logo definition

$$\frac{A}{B} = 0,8$$

$$\frac{D}{C} = 0,46$$

Logo typography: **Potential Neon Regular**

2. Corporate colours

COLOUR	HEXA	RGB	CMYK	PANTONE
BLUE	001A5A	Ro G26 B90	C99 M100 Y40 K12	273C
ORANGE	CE6B00	R206 G107 B0	C8 M75 Y98 K0	7414C

3. Documentation templates

Figure 1 – Deliverable/report template

Figure 2 - Presentation template

Table

Random	Columns	Corbel	Production

Figure 3 - Calculation sheet and table template

4. Leaflet

WHY?

As a project funded by the European Commission, Chess Setup is closely linked with the **European Horizon 2020** work Program. Thus, by implementing the already mentioned heating system, the initiative contributes to the following triple facet of the 2020 Program (based on 2550 figures).

2%
Cut in greenhouse gas emissions
2% of EU energy from renewable sources
Improvement in energy efficiency

Also, the project is aligned with the Energy Performance Building Directive (EPBD, 2010) which states that, by 2020, all new buildings should reach "nearly zero-energy" performance levels using **innovative and cost optimal technologies** with integration of renewable energy sources on site or nearby.

Chess Setup ensures that its system will have a short payback period and a reduced environmental impact compared to conventional systems, due to the low ecological footprint, the simplicity and availability of most of the elements involved.

WHO?

The Consortium gathers 10 members from five European countries:

FRANCE: edenway	GERMANY: 	THE NETHERLANDS: WATERBOS ARCHITECTUUR
SPAIN: VEOLIA IAVOLA WATRIA	UNITED KINGDOM: Electric Cerby University of LULSTER	

USE CASES

Chess Setup will also include **three pilot experiences** carried out in:

SPAIN SANT CUGAT DEL VALLES Sport center	UNITED KINGDOM CORBY New dwellings
 BARCELONA Office refurbishment	

CHESSE SET UP

Combined HEAT Supply System
by using Solar Energy and hEAT (LHP)

www.chess-setup.net
@ChessSetup

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101017463.

WHAT?

Chess Setup has been created to respond to the increasing **heating and domestic hot water** demand in the building sector. The project aim is to design, implement and promote a reliable, efficient and profitable system able to supply heating and hot water in buildings mainly from **renewable sources**.

The proposed system is based on the **optimal combination** of hybrid photovoltaic and solar panels energy production, heat storage and heat pump use. These panels are a key element to achieve **self-sufficiency in buildings**, especially in dense urban areas where the roof availability is one of the most limiting factors.

The integration of **other energy sources** such as biomass or heat waste will also be considered, to make the system suitable for a broad range of conditions. The project will also explore the possibility to integrate other electricity or cooling technologies such as **cogeneration and solar cooling**.

HOW?

During summer there is a **high solar radiation (SR)** and a **low heat demand (HD)**. The share of the collected energy (CH) which is not required to the heat demand supply (HE) is **transferred** to the seasonal water storage tank to be stored.

SUMMER

SR: Solar radiation; HD: Heat demand; CH: Heat collected; HE: Heat demand

In winter, the heat demand increases and the solar radiation (SR) is **lower**. Therefore it is necessary to **absorb the energy stored (SH)** during summer from the seasonal water tank. The heat pump is responsible for transferring the heat and it is done with very **low electrical consumption (EW)**.

WINTER

SR: Solar radiation; HD: Heat demand; CH: Heat collected; HE: Heat demand; SH: Heat stored; EW: Electrical consumption

WHAT FOR?

The main objectives and targets of the project are listed below:

- Implement a new heating solution based on a trio of technologies on a seasonal mode - hybrid photovoltaic-thermal solar panels, a thermal storage system and heat pump.
- Improve the initial system, and make it compatible with renewable energies' back up sources.
- Test and monitor the functioning of this system in different geographical situations and type of building, along 3 use cases and thanks to proper software.
- Develop business models from the use cases in order to industrialize Chess Setup's achievements.
- Reduce the peak of electricity demand, relying on the system inertia, and allow the renewable energies' connection to the grid.
- Reach a reduction greater than 15% of the investment costs compared to other highly efficient heating systems.

5. Associated files

The files associated with this deliverable are listed below:

- CHESS SETUP_D7.2_LogoV.png
- CHESS SETUP_D7.2_LogoH.png
- CHESS SETUP_D7.2_PowerPoint template.pptx
- CHESS SETUP_D7.2_Deliverable template.docx
- CHESS SETUP_D7.2_Excel template.xlsx
- CHESS SETUP_D7.3_Project leaflet.pdf

The visual identity of CHESS SETUP, composed by the associated files and templates, will be present in all documents and communications related to the project. Also, as part of the European Commission H2020 Programme, any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) will display the EU emblem (attached in the header of the present document) and include the following text:

"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 680556."

Finally, public communications will also indicate that *they only reflect the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.*

